

Testing the Beam Interruption Method for ADS Reactivity Monitoring at the GUINEVERE Facility

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ABSTRACT

Reliable and robust reactivity monitoring is essential for the safe operation of Accelerator-Driven Systems (ADS), where a subcritical reactor is sustained by an external neutron source. This work presents a detailed assessment of a reactivity measurement technique based on short, periodic interruptions of the neutron source, using experimental data obtained during the FREYA project at the GUINEVERE facility, which consists on the VENUS-F fast reactor, coupled to the GENEPI-3C accelerator. Three standard core configurations of increasing complexity, together with three perturbed variants, were analyzed using the responses of 11 fission chamber detectors distributed throughout the reactor core.

The study highlights the significant influence of space-energy effects on detector signals during beam interruptions, leading to noticeable detector position-dependent biases in reactivity estimates. To address this issue, detailed Monte-Carlo simulations were performed with the Serpent 2 neutron transport code, employing a homogeneous reactor model to compute space-energy factors that account for these space-energy effects. Application of these factors substantially improves detector-to-detector consistency and brings corrected reactivity values into close agreement with independent reference measurements obtained through the Modified Source Multiplication (MSM) method. Preliminary results confirm both the robustness of the beam-interruption technique and the necessity of space-energy factors for accurate reactivity monitoring in ADS systems.

Keywords: Reactivity monitoring, Sub-criticality, ADS experiments, Space-energy effects, Monte-Carlo simulations

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of radioactive waste management, the incineration of minor actinides (MA) is a process that is proposed as an alternative to deep geological storage, and in which Accelerator Driven Systems (ADS) could play a central role. An ADS consists of a subcritical fast reactor coupled to an external neutron source. The subcriticality of the reactor allows for a more flexible fuel composition, as well as a high MA transmutation capability, as long as this subcriticality can be ensured at every moment.

Consequently, it is essential to monitor the subcriticality of the reactor in real time while it is in operation, through online reactivity measurements. With this objective, the Euratom FREYA (Fast Reactor Experiments for hYbrid Applications) project was set up, running from 2011 to 2016. As part of it, a series of reactivity measurements were carried out at the GUINEVERE ADS facility [1]. This facility,

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situated in the SCK·CEN research center in Mol, Belgium, coupled the fast neutron subcritical reactor VENUS-F to an external neutron source consisting of the deuteron accelerator GENEPI-3C and a tritium target to ensure the conversion of deuterons to neutrons via the $T(d, n)\alpha$ fusion reaction. During these experiments, the chosen reactivity measurement technique was to perform periodical, short interruptions of the neutron source, subsequently analyzing how the neutron flux decreased.

In order to set up a reliable and robust method for reactivity measurements, assessing its trustworthiness and identifying the biases and uncertainties would be of paramount importance in the case of a power ADS. To do so, it is fundamental to study in great detail the space-energy effects, that is to say, the neutron flux deformations during beam interruptions that can impact the measure of the reactivity depending on the position of the detectors and their sensitivity to neutron energy.

The work described here consists in the analysis of data from the FREYA experimental campaign. Three standard configurations for the core of VENUS-F are discussed, in addition to three variants that were modified to simulate several abnormal effects. These data sets formed a more stringent set of tests for the reactivity measurement techniques compared with previous FREYA experiments performed with simpler core configurations [2]. Simulation work using the neutron transport code Serpent 2 [3] is also carried out, from which space-energy factors for the aforementioned space-energy effects can be extracted.

2. THE GUINEVERE FACILITY

Figure 1. 3-dimensional model of the GUINEVERE facility.

2.1. The External Neutron Source

GENEPI-3C, designed and built by a collaboration of CNRS-IN2P3 laboratories, provided an external neutron source by accelerating deuterons up to ≈ 220 keV and sending them onto a titanium-tritium (TiT) target located at the center of the reactor core. This caused $T(d, n)^4\text{He}$ fusion reactions, which yielded ≈ 14 -MeV neutrons emitted almost isotropically inside the core.

For the work presented here, GENEPI-3C was operated in continuous mode with short, periodic beam interruptions.

The accelerator was also equipped with two Si detectors covered with Al foils that served the purpose of neutron source monitoring. The most relevant for this work, API, could detect alpha particles from the $T(d, n)^4\text{He}$ reaction as well as protons from the parasitic $D(d, p)T$. The count rates obtained from this detector were therefore used to check the variations of the neutron source intensity over time.

2.2. The VENUS-F Reactor

VENUS-F is a modular fast neutron research reactor that can function both by itself as a critical reactor, or as part of an ADS as a subcritical reactor. It is contained in a cylindrical vessel of approximately 80 cm in radius and 140 cm in height. It consists of radial, top and bottom lead reflectors and a stainless steel casing, containing a 12x12 array where different types of assemblies can be distributed. Each of these assemblies has a section of $\approx 8 \times 8 \text{ cm}^2$.

The fuel assemblies used in this work presented a 5x5 grid, surrounded by lead plates and filled with 13 rodlets of 30 wt% U-235/U enriched metallic uranium fuel, 4 alumina (Al_2O_3) rodlets and 8 lead rodlets, disposed in a symmetrical pattern. Six mobile fuel assemblies were specially designed with an upper section composed of boron carbide, enabling them to operate as Safety Rods (SR) when inserted into the reactor core and to function as standard fuel assemblies when withdrawn. Two movable boron carbide assemblies functioned as Control Rods (CR) and a final lightweight neutron-absorbing element, the POAR rod, was employed for rod drop experiments. A number of holes of various sizes could be found both all over the 12x12 array and in the outer lead reflector, with the purpose of accommodating neutron detectors.

To facilitate the identification of the various assemblies and detector positions, an arbitrary coordinate system was defined for the 12×12 matrix. The upper-left position was labeled (-6, 6) and the lower-right position (6, -6); with no element corresponding to (0, 0). Also, the cavities of the outer reflector were designated, from left to right, as A1, B1, C1, A2, B2, and C2.

For this work, a total of 11 fission chamber detectors were used, 10 of them filled with different masses of 92 to 93% pure ^{235}U , with only one using 99.965% pure ^{238}U as a deposit. The locations of these detectors were, from closest to farthest to the center of the core: (-3, 1), (4, -3), (1, 5), (-1, -5), (4, 4), (-4, -4), (6, -6), (-6, 6), C1, A1 and C2 (this last one corresponding to the ^{238}U detector).

A total of six configurations were studied for the present work. First, three standard configurations, called SC5, SC7 and SC8-3, which can be seen in Figure 2. They were designed to have approximately the same reactivity while progressively increasing in complexity by adding and/or rearranging graphite, polyethylene and fuel assemblies. This served the purpose of proving the efficacy of the chosen reactivity measurement technique in increasingly complex environments, with SC8-3 being representative of a core of an industrial ADS like MYRRHA [4]. Afterwards, another three versions of SC8-3 were set up, where one fuel assembly was altered to simulate anomalous effects, again to test the limits of the chosen reactivity measurement method as well as to obtain insight on how space-energy effects emerge. The first of them simulated fuel agglomeration by modifying fuel assembly (-1, 4) to relocate most of the uranium rodlets in the lower third of its height. The second one simulated leakage increase due to water ingress by replacing lead assembly at (-1, 5) by a polyethylene one with a cavity in the middle. The third one simulated moderation increase due to water ingress by replacing two lead plates by polyethylene plates in assembly (-3, 4).

With the objective of testing beam interruptions as a reactivity measurement method, the reactivity values of the reactor configurations were measured beforehand [5] using the Modified Source Multiplication (MSM) method, which was systematically used for estimating the reactivity of the subcritical VENUS-F configurations. [6].

Figure 2. Top view of the three standard VENUS-F core configurations, with their corresponding MSM reactivity values and uncertainties. Yellow represents lead, orange for stainless steel, dark blue for fuel assemblies, light blue for polyethylene, green for graphite, red for control rods and violet for safety rods.

3. REACTIVITY MEASUREMENTS AND SPACE-ENERGY EFFECTS

3.1. Fundamentals

Throughout this work, the chosen reactivity monitoring technique is based on performing periodical, short interruptions of the deuteron beam, and hence of the neutron source. This method had already been proven to be a good candidate, as prior to this study it had been tested in simpler configurations, obtaining very satisfactory results [2]. This technique is based on Point Kinetics, which is known to be a very good approximation for time dependent reactor behaviors close to criticality in the absence of a significant external neutron source [7]. On top of that, a series of constraints must be met by the amount of beam interruptions (n_{BT}), the time between two interruptions (t_{on}) and the total period of the interruptions (T) [8]. If all of this conditions are met, and considering only one group of delayed neutrons, the evolution in time of the neutron population ($n(t)$) during a beam interruption can be expressed as follows:

$$n(t) \propto \left[\exp\left(\frac{\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}} t\right) - \left(\frac{\beta_{\text{eff}}}{\rho}\right) \left(\frac{t_{on}}{T}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\lambda \rho}{\beta_{\text{eff}} - \rho}(t - T)\right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the reactivity, Λ_{eff} the mean generation time, β_{eff} the effective delayed-neutron fraction and λ the decay constant of the delayed-neutron group.

The first term on equation (1) describes the fast, prompt decay of the neutron population after the interruption of the external neutron source, with the second term showing a slower decay related to fission reactions driven by the delayed neutrons. This equation allows one to extract expressions for the neutron population before the interruption (n_0) and after the prompt decay (n_1) [8]. From them, we can obtain an expression for the reactivity, that allows for it to be measured by knowing n_0 and n_1 :

$$\rho_{\S} = \frac{\rho}{\beta_{\text{eff}}} = \left(\frac{t_{on}}{T}\right) \left(\frac{n_1 - n_0}{n_1}\right) \quad (2)$$

As the neutron population cannot be directly measured experimentally, it is usual to adopt the reason-

able approximation that the detector count rate is proportional to the neutron population. Given all this, it is also important to take into account that the validity of Point Kinetics can be put in question when considering a subcritical reactor, and a setting where the shape of the neutron flux is not constant over time.

3.2. Data Analysis

During experiments, neutron source interruptions were performed with a 25 ms period, with the beam being off during 2 ms per period. The fission chambers distributed all over the reactor counted fission events that were time stamped with a 300 μs margin around the beam interruptions themselves, with only scalars being recorded the rest of the time to save storage space.

In order to have sufficient statistics to correctly carry out the analysis of the data, beam interruption histograms like the ones shown in Figure 3 have been constructed by piling up the detector responses for each beam interruption during day-long experiments. From them, n_0 can be estimated by integrating the neutron counts during the last 300 μs before the interruption of the source, while the same thing is done for n_1 with the last 500 μs of the beam interruption. Before that, however, two corrections were applied to the datasets in order to improve the accuracy of the obtained reactivities.

Figure 3. Evolution of normalized, dead-time corrected count rates during multiple beam interruptions for four detectors located right outside of the reactor core (orange), on the outer edge of the inner reflector (magenta) and on the inner (green) and outer (blue) edges of the outer reflector.

The first of these corrections accounts for the fact that n_0 estimation can be greatly affected when the temporal profile of the neutron source starts to differ from an ideal square shape. Therefore, data is retrieved from the API and PI source monitoring detectors, and used to calculate a form factor to correct the value of n_0 [2].

Second, count rate values can get really high for the highest deposit fission chambers located close to the reactor core, which means that dead time has to be taken into account. Admitting that the effect of dead time can be described by a non-paralyzable model, the corrected count rate n is given by the following expression:

$$n = \frac{m}{1 - m\tau} \quad (3)$$

with m being the measured count rate and τ the detectors dead time parameter.

This dead time parameters had been measured before for the majority of the detectors, and thus were available directly [9]. However, for the rest of the detectors, τ had to be estimated with an approximate method: since the reactivity measurement must not depend on the intensity of the neutron source, and knowing that n_0 is much more affected by dead time than n_1 , τ was inferred by minimizing the difference between reactivity values measured with high and low beam intensities for the same detector, detector location and reactor configuration.

As can be seen in Figure 3, the shape of the neutron population decay during a beam interruption changes noticeably for detectors in different locations inside the reactor. These discrepancies with Point Kinetics happen due to space-energy effects, which can cause important biases on reactivity estimations.

Figure 4 shows reactivity values obtained using Formula (2) as green squares (in most cases, the error bars are smaller than the symbols). A significant dependence of the reactivity value with the detector position can be observed. It is worth commenting the case of the detector in A1, whose reactivity value is a clear outlier for every configuration. This is due to its position, the closest to the reactor edge, that allows neutrons scattered back by the concrete walls surrounding the reactor to reach this detector, which prevents the delayed neutron plateau to be attained within the 2 ms source interruption. Even though the detector in C2 holds a similar position, its ^{238}U deposit is much less sensitive to wall returns due to its fission energy threshold.

Figure 4. Reactivity values for each of the three base configurations (first row), the three modified versions of SC8-3 (second row) and difference between values of each modified configuration and SC8-3 (third row). MSM reference values are represented by dashed red lines, with their uncertainties in solid red lines. Green squares represent raw reactivity values, and blue circles the ones corrected for space-energy effects. Vertical black dashed lines separate detectors by their distance to the center of the core, with the closest being on the left.

The third row of Figure 4 shows the reactivity worth of each core perturbation with respect to the SC8-3 configuration. This allows to see the general effect of the perturbations on reactivity. When leakage is increased, reactivity goes significantly down, as more leakage implies a bigger amount of lost neutrons. Moderation going up means an increase on the probability of fissions occurring, which explains the notable rise on reactivity. Finally, fuel agglomeration at the bottom of one assembly causes a very small increase on reactivity, as the total amount of fuel stays the same and the mean free path of neutrons is rather large in the fast VENUS-F reactor.

3.3. Simulations and Space-Energy Factors

For the purpose of studying space-energy effects and adequately correcting for them during reactivity measurements, Monte-Carlo simulations were carried out using the Serpent 2 neutron transport code [3]. The six different configurations of the VENUS-F core were modeled. For the fuel assemblies, a homogeneous model was adopted, in which each assembly is treated as a homogeneous mixture of the components of its individual constituents. This results in a reduction of computational time with the tradeoff on precision staying acceptable according to prior experiments [10].

Inside of the built geometries, neutron transport has been simulated in two different ways, first by power iteration, which gives a reactivity value for the neutron transport model (ρ_{model}), and then with a fixed 14 MeV neutron source, to get the response of the fission chambers placed in the reactor. This response has been processed in the same way as measured data, calculating reactivity values with expression (2) (ρ_{source}). Using the reactivities obtained with both methods, preliminary space-energy factors for space-energy effects were calculated as:

$$f_{SE} = \frac{\rho_{model}}{\rho_{source}} \quad (4)$$

with the final reactivity value simply being $\rho_{SE} = f_{SE} * \rho_{\S}$.

The corrected reactivity values in Figure 4 are represented by blue circles. Their uncertainties have not yet been obtained due to the elevated computational times required, however their calculation will be the next objective of this work. Looking at the reactivities, it can be observed that after accounting for space-energy effects, the values for different detectors align themselves, reducing the effect of the detector position on the reactivity measurement. Furthermore, the vast majority of the corrected reactivity values fall within 1σ of the MSM value, reinforcing the reliability of the measurement. This is specially interesting for the perturbed configurations, as it can be seen that the space-energy correction works rather well even when introducing small reactivity effects. However, the reactivity worths themselves, on the third row graphs, do not seem to be greatly affected by the correction.

Two notable exceptions can be pointed out: first, the detector in the (4,4) position seems to be an outlier for each of the unperturbed configurations, this behavior being even more noticeable when looking at the difference values on the third row. The reason for this is currently being investigated, with a possible explanation being a malfunction of the fission chamber itself. Second, the corrected reactivity values for the SC5 configuration seem to differ noticeably from the correspondent MSM reference value. It is hypothesized that the MSM value might be incorrect due to the POAR absorbent rod being removed from the reactor during the beam interruption experiments for SC5, but inserted during the corresponding MSM measurement. Research is also being carried out to attempt to confirm this hypothesis.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The reactivity monitoring method for an ADS based on short, periodic interruptions of the external neutron source has been put to test using data collected during the FREYA project experiments at the GUINEVERE facility. Searching for the limits of this technique, three base configurations of increas-

ing complexity and three modified configurations with simulated abnormal effects have been studied, obtaining reactivity values by analyzing the count rates of 11 fission chamber detectors distributed through the VENUS-F reactor core. It is observed that both the shape of the neutron population decay after a beam interruption and the reactivity values show a noteworthy dependence with the detector position, which is associated with space-energy effects. Serpent 2 simulations of the six studied configurations have been used to calculate space-energy factors to account for space-energy effects, which are found to significantly improve the reactivity values with respect to the MSM values used as reference. Future work will include the calculation of uncertainties for the space-energy corrected reactivity values, as well as further simulations using a heterogeneous approach for configuration modeling, with the objective of maximizing the accuracy of correction factors.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Billebaud et al. "The GUINEVERE Project for Accelerator Driven System Physics." In *International Conference GLOBAL 2009*, pp. 1809–1815. Paris, France (2009).
- [2] T. Chevret et al. "Reactivity Measurement of the Lead Fast Subcritical VENUS-F Reactor Using Beam Interruption Experiments." In *PHYSOR 2014 "The Role of Reactor Physics toward a Sustainable Future"*. Kyoto, Japan (2014).
- [3] J. Leppänen et al. "The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 142–150 (2015).
- [4] H. Podlech et al. "The MYRRHA project." In *Joint Accelerator Conferences Website (JACoW)*. Lansing, United States (2019).
- [5] A. Kochetkov, A. Krása, N. Messaoudi, and J.-L. Lecouey. "DELIVERABLE D2.3: MYRRHA Subcritical Mock-up reactivity effects." Technical Report FP7-269665, SCK·CEN (2016).
- [6] J. Lecouey, N. Marie, G. Ban, G. Bianchini, A. Billebaud, M. Carta, S. Chabod, V. Fabrizio, A. Kochetkov, F. Lecolley, et al. "Estimate of the reactivity of the VENUS-F subcritical configuration using a Monte Carlo MSM method." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 83**, pp. 65–75 (2015).
- [7] K. O. Ott and R. J. Neuhold. *Introductory nuclear reactor dynamics*. American nuclear society (1985).
- [8] J.-L. Lecouey. "Reactivity Monitoring of Accelerator Driven Subcritical Reactors." *Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches Université de Caen Normandie* (2020, unpublished).
- [9] A. Bailly. *Mesure de la réactivité d'un réacteur sous critique à neutrons rapides*. Ph.D. thesis, Normandie Université (2022).
- [10] N. Marie et al. "Reactivity monitoring using the area method for the subcritical VENUS-F core within the framework of the FREYA Project." *Technology and Components of Accelerator Driven Systems 2* (2013).